

Supplementary Figure 2. Histogram of the number of shared participants between two groups for each pair of groups across the whole dataset. While shared participants between groups can impact our results by slightly over-estimating our performance, the impact is likely to be low due to the small number of shared participants (2.3 on average). In addition, this has no impact the conclusions of our study on the comparison of performance between different models as all models are trained and evaluated on the same sets of groups.